

Physico-Chemical and Microbiological Studies of Fresh Water Reservoir, Talab Shahi, Dholpur (Rajasthan) India

Paper Id : 19342 Submission Date : 2024-06-19 Acceptance Date : 2024-06-21 Publication Date : 2024-06-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13957486

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/anthology.php#8>

**Mahendra Singh
Lodha**
Research Scholar
Deptt. Of Zoology
M.S.J. Govt. P.G. College
Bharatpur, Rajasthan, India

Rajesh Singh
Research Supervisor
Deptt. Of Zoology
M.S.J. Govt. P.G. College
Bharatpur, Rajasthan,
India

Abstract

Water quality is a critical concern in managing aquatic ecosystems and sustainability of water bodies. The fresh water reservoir, Talab Shahi, situated in Dholpur district of Rajasthan serves as a vital water resource for agriculture, fish production, and various domestic purposes. Given its importance, monitoring and analyzing of physico-chemical and microbiological parameters of water is essential to understand the reservoir's water quality and its suitability for different uses. The water of reservoir analyzed from June 2022 to May 2024 and the main focus on examining the the water quality by assessing key physico-chemical and microbiological parameters. The physico-chemical parameters analyzed include pH, water temperature, color, total alkalinity, turbidity, total acidity, total hardness, chloride, sulphate fluoride, dissolved oxygen (D.O.), nitrate, free CO₂, phosphate, salinity, total dissolved solids (T.D.S.), biochemical oxygen demand (B.O.D.), and chemical oxygen demand (C.O.D.) etc. and microbial contaminants, including *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was systematically monitored across multiple sites within the reservoir.

The result of the physico-chemical and microbiological studies reveals that all the Physico-chemical parameters within the permissible limit except color and turbidity but higher levels of microbial contamination observed. Therefore, the water of the reservoir is unfit for human consumption (drinking) but it is useful for irrigation, fish production and other purposes.

Keywords Physico-Chemical, Microbiological, Water Quality, Talab Shahi Reservoir.

Introduction Water is absolutely essential for all the creatures on the earth. It is vital for aquatic animals not only as a habitat but also as a medium for vital biological processes, temperature regulation, and structural support. The physiological functions of these organisms depend on the unique properties of this essential liquid. Despite Earth's appearance of watery abundance, less than 1% of the water is fresh and usable which makes it essential to preserve and manage this precious resource. The water quality can deteriorate rapidly due to various factors, making it unfit for designated uses (Garode and Bhusari, 2017). Freshwater reservoirs play a crucial role in sustaining life on Earth by providing essential resources such as drinking water, irrigation, fisheries, and recreational opportunities. In many regions, especially those with arid climates or limited natural water sources, reservoirs are indispensable for supporting both human populations and local ecosystems. However, as human activities intensify, the health of these reservoirs is increasingly threatened by pollution, overuse, and environmental degradation. Assessing the physico-chemical, microbiological quality and biodiversity within these water bodies is critical for ensuring their sustainability and continued usability.

Objective of study The objective physico-chemical and microbiological studies of fresh water reservoir in special reference to Talab Shahi, Dholpur district of Rajasthan, India.

Review of Literature

Natural and anthropogenic factors influence water quality (Kumar et al., 2017). The combination of municipal waste, religious activities, and animal waste creates a complex pollution scenario that poses significant challenges for water quality management (Mishra and Bhatt, 2019). The microbiological quality of small freshwater reservoirs witnesses the presence of bacterial indicators like *Escherichia coli* and faecal enterococci, as well as fungal contaminants such as Molds and yeasts. The emerging concern of fungal contaminants in water is a serious concern that needs to be sorted out for the sake of water quality management as well as the aquatic life (Mourão and Martinho, 2022). The various uses of water for the purpose of irrigation, industry, domestic, human consumption, agriculture make it unique (Saxena, 2007). However, the contemporary scenario constituted by urbanization, industrialization, industrial processes and anti-environmental human activities reveals the deterioration in the quality of the water in the reservoirs (Yogita and Jain, 2022). There is significant pollution in the water bodies surrounding the power plant, particularly during the monsoon season when runoff from the plant is highest (Tripathi et al., 2014). The human activities and natural processes make a deep influence on water quality of rivers and other water bodies (Nayak and Mohanty, 2018).

The surface water quality is degrading day-by-day making it difficult for man and animals including aquatic animals to drink pure water. It is high demand of the times that the interplay between monsoon patterns and water quality should be understood and be tested and maintained accordingly (Khound et al., 2012). The anthropogenic contamination has a deep impact on water bodies. There is an utmost need for proper monitoring and management of water quality indicators to prevent further degradation of natural water resources (Dwivedi and Tripathi, 2016). There are several reasons of the degradation of the water quality which, with the passage of time, is making the human as well as aquatic life difficult and hard. Global warming is one of them which has drastically caused seasonal variations which lead to contamination of water. There is a critical impact of climatic conditions on water resources as a result of which physico-chemical properties of water are drastically altered (Jeyagowri, Vidhya, Devi, and Tan 2022). The climatic variations do affect the water reservoirs and water bodies which are in the grip of pollution. Moderate levels of nutrients are essential for supporting aquatic life and to maintain aquatic balance (Kashyap, 2021).

Methodology

Talab Shahi (also called Talab-e-Shahi) is a fresh water reservoir located at 26-degree 37 north latitude and 77-degree 39 east longitude in the Parbati river basin of district Dholpur (Rajasthan). The methodology for this research is designed to comprehensively assess the physico-chemical and microbiological characteristics of water in the Talab Shahi Reservoir over a specified period from June 2022 to May 2024 (for two consecutive years). The aims of present study to investigate trimonthly variation like season-wise June to August (monsoon), September to November (post-monsoon), December to February (winter) and March to May (pre-monsoon) if any, in physico-chemical and microbiological parameters of water. The water samples were collected and analyzed twice a month with definite time interval and samples were collected in clean, airtight non-reacting and specific plastic bottles with capacity of one litre volume. Sampling was conducted in accordance with established protocols to ensure accuracy and reliability of data.

Water samples were collected from four predetermined sites (S_1 , S_2 , S_3 and S_4) within the Talab Shahi Reservoir. These sites were strategically selected to represent different parts of the reservoir, ensuring a comprehensive assessment of the water quality across the entire water body. The sampling site S_1 : located Near Chandani chowk towards Bharat Nirman Rajiv Seva Kendra, S_2 : located towards the guest house, S_3 : located towards the village Nizampur, and S_4 : located towards the village Jore ka Pura.

The collected water samples were analyzed and find out physicochemical parameters by various method as given by APHA (2005) like- pH (Electrometric Method), Temperature (On the spot by portable water analysis kit), Color (Spectrophotometer Method), Total Alkalinity (Titration Method), Turbidity (By Nephelometric Method), Total Acidity (Titration Method), Total Hardness (EDTA Titration Method), Lead (Dithizone Method), Chloride (By Silver nitrate titrimetric Method), Sulphate (Turbidimetric Method by Spectrophotometer), Fluoride (By SPADNS Method), Dissolved Oxygen (Winkler-azide Method), Nitrate (By

Rubbing Method by Spectrophotometer), Free CO₂ (Standard alkali titrimetric Method), Phosphate (By stannous chloride Method by Spectrophotometer), Salinity (By Silver nitrate Method), Total Dissolved Solids (By electronic Method), Biochemical Oxygen Demand (By five-day incubation at 20^{0C} with serial dilute method), Chemical Oxygen Demand (By Potassium Dichromate Titration Method) and microbiological parameters like- *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were analyzed by serial dilution and plate culture technique. The obtained primary data were subjected to statistical analysis to find out an average value and standard error and compare average values with limits of standards to evaluate the water quality of reservoir.

Result and Discussion

Table: -01 Minimum and Maximum Average value of Physico-chemical and Microbiological parameters of Talab Shahi Reservoir, Dholpur (Rajasthan) during June 2022 to May 2024.

Parameter (Unit)	Minimum Average Value	Months (Season)	Maximum Average Value	Months (Season)	Permissible Limit (BIS:2012)
pH	6.63	Dec.2023 to Feb.2024 (Winter)	7.02	March to May-2023 (Pre-monsoon)	6.5 - 8.5
Temperature (°C)	15.4	Dec.2023 to Feb.2024 (Winter)	29.3	June to August-2023 (Monsoon)	-
Color (Hazen Unit)	196.0	Dec.2022 to Feb.2023 (Winter)	410.6	June to August-2023 (Monsoon)	≤ 15
Total Alkalinity (mg/L)	80.2	June to August-2023 (Monsoon)	128.3	March to May-2023 (Pre-monsoon)	≤ 200
Turbidity (NTU)	26.5	Dec.2022 to Feb.2023 (Winter)	59.2	June to August-2023 (Monsoon)	≤ 5.0
Total Acidity (mg/L)	8.1	Sept. to Nov.2022 (post-monsoon)	11.0	March to May-2023 (Pre-monsoon)	-
Total Hardness (mg/L)	71.2	June to August-2023 (Monsoon)	92.8	March to May-2023 (Pre-monsoon)	≤ 300
Chloride (mg/L)	23.6	June to August-2022 (Monsoon)	40.05	March to May-2023 (Pre-monsoon)	≤ 1000
Sulphate (mg/L)	3.36	March to May-2024 (Pre-monsoon)	6.41	June to August-2022 (Monsoon)	≤ 400
Fluoride (mg/L)	0.23	June to August-2022 (Monsoon)	0.96	Dec.2022 to Feb.2023 (Winter)	≤1.5
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	5.32	March to May-2024 (Pre-monsoon)	9.05	June to August-2022 (Monsoon)	6.5 -12
Nitrate (mg/L)	5.83	June to August-2022 (Monsoon)	11.92	March to May-2023 (Pre-monsoon)	≤ 45
Free CO ₂ (mg/L)	4.83	June to August-2022 (Monsoon)	8.97	March to May-2023 (Pre-monsoon)	≤ 10
Phosphate (mg/L)	0.019	Dec.2022 to Feb.2023 (Winter)	0.060	June to August-2022 (Monsoon)	≤ 0.1
Salinity (mg/L)	70.3	Dec.2022 to Feb.2023 (Winter)	116.6	March to May-2024 (Pre-monsoon)	≤ 1500
Total Dissolved Solids (mg/L)	161.8	Dec.2022 to Feb.2023 (Winter)	238.2	June to August-2023 (Monsoon)	≤ 500
Biochemical Oxygen Demand (mg/L)	2.52	Dec.2022 to Feb.2023 (Winter)	7.43	June to August-2023 (Monsoon)	≤ 30
Chemical Oxygen Demand (mg/L)	39.7	June to August-2022 (Monsoon)	84.8	March to May-2023 (Pre-monsoon)	≤ 200
<i>E. coli</i> /100 ml water	268.0	Dec.2022 to Feb.2023 (Winter)	400.0	June to August-2023 (Monsoon)	≤ 10.0/100 ml water (ISI Standard)
<i>Salmonella</i> /100 ml water	176.0	Dec.2022 to Feb.2023 (Winter)	327.0	June to August-2023 (Monsoon)	≤ 10.0/100 ml water (ISI Standard)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> /100 ml water	116.0	Dec.2022 to Feb.2023 (Winter)	216.0	June to August-2023 (Monsoon)	≤ 10.0/100 ml water (ISI Standard)

TA- Total Alkalinity T.Acidity- Total Acidity TH- Total Hardness DO- Dissolved Oxygen
 TDS- Total Dissolved Solids BOD- Biochemical Oxygen Demand COD- Chemical
 Oxygen Demand

Fig. 01 Minimum and Maximum Average value of Physico-chemical parameters of Talab Shahi Reservoir, Dholpur (Rajasthan) during June 2022 to May 2024.

Fig. 02 Minimum and Maximum Average value of Microbes in Talab Shahi Reservoir, Dholpur (Rajasthan) during June 2022 to May 2024.

Physico-chemical Study

The physico-chemical parameters of water from Talab Shahi Reservoir analyzed over the period from June 2022 to May 2024 reveals significant variations as following-

pH

The average pH values 6.63 and 7.02, indicating a neutral to slightly acidic water environment. The highest average pH (7.02) observed during March to May-2023(Pre-monsoon) and lowest (6.63) during Dec.2023 to Feb.2024 (Winter). The pH values of reservoir suitable to aquatic health and fish production.

Temperature (°C)

The water temperature shows considerable seasonal variation, with the highest average recorded during the summer months (29.3°C in June to August 2023) and the lowest in winter (15.4°C in December 2023 to February 2024). Temperature plays a pivotal role in microbial metabolism and growth rates, which in turn affects the spatial distribution of different microbial species within the water column. There is a complex interaction between environmental factors, such as water temperature, nutrient availability, and the physical structure of the reservoir, and their influence on the distribution and composition of microbial communities (Guo et al., 2021).

Color (Hazen Unit)

Color values, which indicate the presence of dissolved organic and inorganic substances, were highest in the monsoon seasons, with a maximum average value of 410.6 Hazen units in June to August 2023, suggesting increased organic material and sediment load during this period. Lower average color value of 196.0 observed in winter season (Dec.2022 to Feb.2023).

Total Alkalinity (mg/L)

The highest average value of 128.3 mg/L during March to May-2023 (Pre-monsoon)suggests significant buffering capacity, which helps maintain pH stability and lowest average alkalinity of 80.2 mg/L recorded in June to August 2023 (Monsoon). High alkalinity indicating severe contamination resulting from unregulated industrial activities and poor waste management practices not only makes the water unsafe for drinking and irrigation but also threatens the broader ecosystem (Hameed and Kumar, 2018).

Turbidity (mg/L)

Turbidity of reservoir's water followed a similar trend like color with maximum average value of 59.2 NTU during the monsoon season (June to August-2023), reflecting higher suspended solids, likely due to runoff and inflow during the monsoon. The lowest turbidity of 26.5 NTU was observed in December 2022 to February 2023, indicating clearer water.

Total Acidity (mg/L)

Total Acidity levels reservoir's water indicate the presence of acidic substances in the water. The highest average of total acidity 11.0 ppm was observed in March to May 2023, while the lowest average of 8.1 ppm was recorded in Sept. to Nov.2022 (post-monsoon).

Total Hardness (mg/L)

Total hardness showed moderate values peaks 92.8 in the pre-monsoon (March to May-2023) and lowest average value 71.2 during June to August-2023 (Monsoon) indicating the water's capacity to buffer against pH changes and the presence of calcium and magnesium ions. Total Hardness of reservoir water suitable aquatic animals and fish production.

Chloride (mg/L)

Chloride concentrations ranged within permissible limit. The highest average chloride concentration of 40.05 ppm was recorded in March to May 2023 during Pre-monsoon, while the lowest average of 23.6 ppm was observed in June to August 2022. The observed chloride levels are within safe limits, ensuring that the water remains conducive for aquatic life.

Fluoride (mg/L)

The highest average fluoride concentration of 0.96 ppm was observed in December 2022 to February 2023, and the lowest average of 0.23 ppm in June to August 2022. The observed fluoride levels are generally within safe limits, ensuring that the water remains suitable for consumption and supports aquatic life.

Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)

Dissolved oxygen (DO) levels were highest in the monsoon season (9.05 ppm in June to August 2022), which is crucial for respiration of aquatic life, while lowest value 5.32 was observed in the March to May-2024 (Pre-monsoon), possibly due to higher temperatures and increased biological activity. The observed DO levels are within safe limits, ensuring the suitability of water for aquatic life.

Nitrate (mg/L)

The highest average nitrate concentration of 11.92 ppm was recorded in March to May 2023, while the lowest average of 5.83 ppm was observed in June to August 2022. The observed nitrate levels were relatively higher during the pre-monsoon months, suggesting nutrient inflows from agricultural runoff.

Free CO₂ (mg/L)

The highest average values were observed in March to May 2023 (8.97 ppm), while the lowest average values were in June to August 2022 (4.83 ppm). Free CO₂ is essential for photosynthesis in aquatic plants but high levels can affect fish respiration. The observed levels support a healthy aquatic ecosystem.

Phosphate (mg/L)

Phosphate is a vital nutrient for plant growth, but elevated levels can lead to algal blooms, which can deplete oxygen levels and harm aquatic life. The observed phosphate levels with maximum and minimum average values respectively 0.06 (June to August-2022) and 0.019 (Dec.2022 to Feb.2023).

Sulphate (mg/L)

Notably, the highest average sulphate level 6.41 was consistently recorded during the monsoon periods (June to Aug.2022), while the lowest average level 3.36 was observed during March to May-2024 (Pre-monsoon).

Salinity (mg/L)

Salinity is an important parameter that influences the ionic composition of water, which can affect the osmoregulation processes in aquatic organisms. Average highest and lowest value of salinity respectively 116.6 (March to May-2024) and 70.3 (Dec.2022 to Feb.2023). The salinity levels within safe limit and suitable for aquatic animals.

Total Dissolved Solids (mg/L)

The highest average TDS of 238.2 ppm was recorded in June to Aug.2023, while the lowest average of 161.8 ppm was observed in December 2022 to February 2023. The observed TDS levels support aquatic life and ensures the overall health of the reservoir.

Biochemical Oxygen Demand (mg/L)

The highest average value was 7.43 ppm recorded in monsoon season (June to August 2023) and lower 2.52 in winter season (December 2022 to February 2023). Higher BOD values suggest increased organic pollution and indicating the amount of organic matter present in the water.

Chemical Oxygen Demand (mg/L)

Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) values of water were under the permissible limit. The highest average of 84.8 ppm observed in March to May 2023, and the lowest average value of

39.77 ppm in June to August 2022. High COD indicate increased organic pollution.

Microbiological Study

The analysis of reservoir's water reveals the presence of bacteria such as *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), *Salmonella*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* that contaminate the water of the reservoir as following-

Escherichia coli (*E. coli*)

E. coli is a fecal coliform bacterium commonly found in the intestines of warm-blooded animals, including humans. Its presence in water is a strong indication of faecal contamination. The highest average 400.0/100 ml of water were recorded during the monsoon season (June to August 2023), indicate the surface runoff carrying faecal matter from surrounding areas into the reservoir and lowest average 268.0/100 ml of water during (Dec.2022 to Feb.2023) winter season.

Salmonella

The highest average value 327.0/100 ml water of *Salmonella* observed during monsoon season (June to August 2023) reflecting increased runoff and the introduction of contaminants from the surroundings into the reservoir. The lower average level 176.0/100 ml of water recorded during winter season (Dec.2022 to Feb.2023) due to reduced contamination from surface runoff.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa

Higher average count (216.0/100 ml water) of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* observed during monsoon season-June to August 2023 and lowest average count 116.0/100 ml of water followed the same trend and reason as *E. coli* and *Salmonella*

Conclusion All the physico-chemical parameters analysed during study were under permissible limit except colour and turbidity. Value of both the parameter in water higher due to presence of dissolved organic matter, such as humic substances from decaying vegetation, and inorganic materials like clay and silt particles. The microbiological analysis of Talab Shahi Reservoir has revealed significant contamination issues, with persistent and high levels of *E. coli*, *Salmonella*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The water of reservoir is useful for fishing, irrigation, washing, bathing and other uses but unfit for human consumption (drinking) due to excess color, turbidity, decaying organic material and heavy contamination of microbes. The seasonal variations and spatial differences observed in the parameters are indicative of the dynamic nature of the reservoir's ecosystem, influenced by both natural processes and anthropogenic activities.

These findings highlight the urgent need for improved water quality management practices to protect public health and ensure the sustainability of the reservoir. Addressing these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach, including enhanced waste management, regular monitoring, public education, ecological restoration, and innovative research. By implementing these strategies, we can safeguard the water quality of Talab Shahi Reservoir, ensuring it remains a vital resource for the communities that depend on it and for the preservation of the surrounding ecosystem.

References

1. Dwivedi, A. P., & Tripathi, I. P. Analysis of Physico-chemical Characteristics of Surface Water Samples Collected from West Zone of Central India. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Chemical Science* (2016).
2. Garode, A. M., & Bhusari, M. R. Bacteriological and Physico-Chemical Analysis of Surface Water in Chikhli Tahsil of Buldana District, India. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 607, 251 (2017). doi: 10.20546/IJCMAS.2017.607.251
3. Guo, J., Zheng, Y., Teng, J., Wang, X., & Song, J. Characteristics of spatial distribution for microbial ecology inside and outside source water reservoir. *Journal of Cleaner Production* (2021).doi: 10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2021.127697.
4. Hameed, M. S., & Kumar, B. S. Analysis of Water Quality Parameters of Surface Water in Tiruchirapalli District, Tamil Nadu, India. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology* (2018).
5. Jeyagowri, B., Vidhya, L., Devi, V. N., & Tan, Y. Physiochemical Characteristics Analysis of Surface Water and Underground Water During the Summer Season. *International Journal of Health Sciences*, (2022). doi: 10.53730/ijhs.v6ns5.9492
6. Kashyap, V. Limnological Studies of the Perennial Waterbody, Govindgarh Lake District Rewa (M.P.). *International Journal of Advanced Academic Studies*, (2022).

doi: 10.33545/27068919.2022.v4.i1d.733

7. Khound, N. J., Phukon, P., & Bhattacharyya, K. G. *Physico-Chemical Studies on Surface Water Quality in the Jia-Bharali River Basin, North Brahmaputra Plain, India. Archives of Applied Science Research (2012).*
8. Kumar, A., Tripathi, M. K., Bhatnagar, P., & Vyash, N. *Physico-Chemical Assessment of Surface Water Quality with Respect to Seasonal Variation Around Amarkantak Thermal Power Plant, Chachai, Madhya Pradesh, India. IOSR Journal of Applied Chemistry, (2014). doi: 10.9790/5736-071022833*
9. Kumar, P., Shyam, R., & Badola, S. *Ichthyofaunal diversity of Tumaria reservoir, Kashipur, U.S. Nagar (Uttarakhand). Environment Conservation Journal, (2017). doi: 10.36953/ECJ.2019.20311.*
10. Mishra, R. K., & Bhatt, S. *The Physico-Chemical Assessment of Pollution of Surface Water of Ghats Along the Bank of River Ganga in Varanasi. The Pharma Innovation Journal (2019).*
11. Mourão, A. V., & Martinho, S. *Potential Hazard to Human and Animal Health from Bacterial and Fungal Contaminants in Small Freshwater Reservoirs. Environmental Science and Pollution Research, (2022). doi: 10.3390/ecerph-4-13071.*
12. Nayak, S. K., & Mohanty, C. R. *Influence of Physico-Chemical Parameters on Surface Water Quality: A Case Study of the Brahmani River, India. Arabian Journal of Geosciences, (2018). doi: 10.1007/S12517-018-3887-6*
13. Rawat, Aakash & Bagri, Dharendra Singh & Kumar, Sudhir. *Water quality assessment of tehri dam reservoir in the context of its potential in aquaponics, Uttarakhand (2019).. 10.13140/RG.2.2.22786.43202.*
14. Saxena, M.M. *Trophic State Indices in Water Quality Monitoring. Proceeding of NSL 2007, pp.24-26. (2007).*
15. Yogita, & Jain, S. *Assessment of Surface Water from Physicochemical Parameters. International Journal of Health Sciences, (2022). doi: 10.53730/ijhs.v6ns2.7150*